

Ethnographer, Society, and Art: Symbiosis of Ethnology, Art and the Discourse of Soviet Colonialism in Latvia

Version 1

Description

The project in humanities and arts aims to create new knowledge about social processes during the Soviet occupation of Latvia, promoting public awareness of them through research into the history of ethnology and how the ethnographic heritage was utilized in applied art. Since independence was regained, this will be the first academic assessment of Soviet-period ethnology, enhancing public appreciation of the system of knowledge production, dissemination, and control as it was under the Soviet totalitarian regime and of the role that ethnography and art played in preserving national identity. Archive records and other written historical sources will be used to investigate how ethnological knowledge was created and how it was employed, both in the service of Soviet ideological aims and also as a resource for strengthening national identity under conditions of colonialism.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science

Grant

Fundamental and Applied
Research Projects

Researchers

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Organizations

Univeristy of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: *Ethnographer, Society, and Art: Symbiosis of Ethnology, Art and the Discourse of Soviet Colonialism in Latvia*

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Organizations:

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: Latvian Council of Science

Grants: Fundamental and Applied Research Projects

Project: *Ethnographer, Society, and Art: Symbiosis of Ethnology and Art and Discourse of the Soviet Colonialism in Latvia*

3. License

License: [CC-BY-4.0](#)

Access Rights: [Public](#)

Publication Date: [2024-05-30](#)

4. Templates

Descriptions

Publications of ethnographers in the Latvian SSR 1948-1989

The publications of ethnographers of the Latvian SSR as a set of texts provide significant evidence of the development of the field of ethnology during the Soviet occupation period. One way to identify the set of publications is to create a unified bibliography. Here, the articles are systematized from one issue of publications—"Arheoloģija un Etnogrāfija".

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The dataset is based on bibliographic information about ethnographers' publications, which reflect research topics, methodology, and factual material.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Textual data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

XLS

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

1000

KB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

There is no selected bibliography of publications of ethnographers in the period of the Soviet occupation.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

to researchers, students, and others

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

No

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

No

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.3.3 Other relevant remarks

The bibliography contains entries in both Latin and Cyrillic script, which hinders the free conversion of this information into other systems.

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2026-12-31

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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